

Title page:

Title: Circular linkages between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity are limited to topsoil at the continental scale

Heading: Decoupling of soil diversity, fertility and plant productivity as a function of soil depth.

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Summary

- The current theoretical framework suggests that tripartite positive feedback relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity, are universal. However, empirical evidence for these relationships at the continental scale and across different soil depths is lacking.
- We investigate the continental-scale relationships between the diversity of microbial and invertebrate-based soil food webs, fertility and aboveground plant productivity at 289 sites and two soil depths, *i.e.*, 0-10 and 20-30 cm, across Australia.
- Soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity are strongly positively related in surface soils. Conversely, in the deeper soil layer, the relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity weaken considerably, most likely as a result of a reduction in biodiversity and fertility with depth. Further modeling suggested that strong positive associations among soil biodiversity-fertility and fertility-plant productivity are limited to the upper soil layer (0-10cm), after accounting for key factors, such as distance from equator, altitude, climate and physicochemical soil properties.
- These findings highlight the importance of surface soil biodiversity for soil fertility; and suggest that any loss of surface soil could potentially break the links between soil biodiversity-fertility and/or fertility-plant productivity, which can negatively impact nutrient cycling and food production, upon which future generations depend.

Key words: Soil biodiversity; plant productivity; terrestrial ecosystems; ecosystem functionality; bacteria; eukaryotes.

Introduction

A universal circular mechanism, including positive feedback cycles between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity is implied in current ecological theories (Wardle et al. 2004; van der Heijden et al. 2008; Hol et al. 2015; Nielsen et al. 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016; Soliveres et al. 2016). However, empirical evidence for such a mechanism is lacking. Some of the major gaps in our knowledge are outlined below. Firstly, previous work has focused on isolated parts of this circular association, providing specific evidence for the relationship between soil biodiversity-fertility, biodiversity-plant productivity or plant productivity-fertility (Wagg et al. 2014; Brady & Weil 2002; Nielsen et al. 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016; Soliveres et al. 2016). However, we lack initiatives aiming to disentangle the magnitude and direction of these relationships when assessed in combination. Secondly, most biodiversity-ecosystem functioning studies have focused on one or several components of soil fertility or biodiversity. However, the links between the diversity of multiple soil trophic levels and components of soil fertility and plant production need to be considered simultaneously to achieve an integrated understanding of the role of biodiversity for ecosystem functioning (Wagg et al. 2014; Soliveres et al. 2016). Finally, previous studies have assessed the relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity under very specific ecological contexts, e.g., within a particular biome on Earth or within a particular soil depth (Wagg et al. 2014; Hol et al. 2015; Nielsen et al. 2015; Soliveres et al. 2016; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016). This in turn, limits our understanding on the circumstances in which the tripartite relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity occur, and, most importantly, on whether this circular mechanism is universal.

The top soil is key for food production and highly vulnerable to degradation and erosion (Jobbágy & Jackson 2000; 2001; Banwart 2011). The soil surface is often covered by litter from aboveground communities and commonly contains the highest concentrations of soil organic matter (Banwart 2011; Jobbágy & Jackson 2001). Moreover, soil biodiversity and fertility have been found to decrease with depth as the amount and diversity of nutrients, but also the concentration of oxygen, become limiting (Hooper et al. 2000; Jobbágy & Jackson 2001). In addition to variations with soil depth, it has also been shown that in subsurface layers, microbial community composition is driven less by these edaphic properties, compared to surface soils, and more by geogenic factors and/or stochastic processes (Powell et al. 2015; Reith et al. 2015). The essential co-occurrence of resource inputs from aboveground communities with high soil biodiversity may, therefore, support the strongest linkages between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity at a topsoil level. However, reductions in soil biodiversity and fertility with soil depth can potentially break the link between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity in the subsoil. In this regard, if tripartite linkages between soil biodiversity, fertility and

plant productivity are limited to the topsoil, then, any loss of the top layer of soil due to environmental change will significantly constrain our ability to provide food for our growing population. Thus, assessing if these tripartite linkages are maintained across deep soil layers or if they are limited to the top few centimeters below the soil surface is a fundamental requirement for developing appropriate monitoring, management and conservation policies, and for predicting how ecosystem functioning will respond under changing environments. Such guidelines are urgently required, because soils are highly vulnerable to global environmental drivers, e.g., climate change, landuse-intensification and desertification (Banwart 2011; Maestre et al. 2015), which are acting to reduce plant productivity, biodiversity and fertility (Gans et al. 2005; Wall et al. 2010; Nielsen et al. 2015; Maestre et al. 2015). In this study, we tested the hypothesis that the positive associations between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity are demonstrable at large spatial scales, but limited to the first top centimeters of soil. To test this hypothesis, we used standardized methods for sampling and analyses of soil fertility and diversity of microbial and invertebrate-based soil food webs at 289 sites and two soils depths, *i.e.*, 0-10 and 20-30 cm, across the Australian continent.

Material and Methods

Study sites.

We used a subset of sample locations (289) across Australia (Fig. 1) from the Biome of Australia Soil Environments (BASE) project (Bissett et al. 2016). This subset of plots had available information on soil biodiversity at multiple trophic levels: bacteria (16S rRNA), fungi (ITS) and eukaryotes (18S rRNA)(Table S1). Samples and field information were collected between 2011 and 2014. Soil samples were collected according to the methods described at the BASE data-portal (Bissett et al. 2016). In brief, at each plot (25 x 25 m quadrat), composite soil samples (nine discrete soil samples) at two depth ranges (0.1 m and 0.3 m) were collected. By systematically collecting soil samples from two discontinuous depths we aimed to alleviate the dependency of surface and shallow subsurface samples and to allow comparison of soil samples at the continental scale. A total of 578 soil samples (289 sites x two depths) were included in this study. Each sample was separated into two subsamples. The first subsample, used for molecular analyses, was frozen and transported to the Adelaide node of the Australian Genome Research Facility (AGRF) laboratories for DNA extraction. The second subsample was air-dried and transported to CSBP laboratories, Perth, Australia for chemical and physical analyses. At the time of sampling all other contextual data were collected, including sample location (coordinates taken at the center point of the sampling quadrat) and elevation above sea level.

Molecular analysis.

Soil DNA was extracted in triplicate, according to the methods employed by the Earth Microbiome Project (<http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/emp-standard-protocols/dna-extraction-protocol/>), at the AGRF. We used an Illumina MiSEQ for sequencing as described in Bissett et al. (2016). Briefly, amplicons targeting the bacterial 16S rRNA gene (27F – 519R) (Lane 1991), fungal ITS region (ITS1F – ITS4) (White et al. 1990) and Eukaryotic 18S rRNA gene (Euk_1391f – EukBr, <http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/emp-standard-protocols/18s/>) were prepared and sequenced for each sample at the Australian Genome Research Facility (Melbourne, Australia) and the Ramaciotti Centre for Genomics (Sydney, Australia). 16S and ITS amplicons were sequenced using 300 bp, paired end sequencing, while 18S amplicon reads were generated using 150 bp paired end sequencing.

Bioinformatic analysis.

Bioinformatic analyses were performed as described in Bissett et al. (2016). Briefly, for rRNA genes, sequence read quality was visually assessed using FastQC (Andrews 2010), sequences were trimmed to remove poor quality bases: 5' end of R1 by 10bp and the 5' end of R2 by 70bp and merged using FLASH (Magoc & Salzberg 2011). Efficacy of merging was checked manually after merging. Sequences < 400bp (16S) or <100bp (18S), or containing N or homopolymer runs of >8bp were removed (MOTHUR v1.34.1; Schloss et al. 2009). The remaining sequences were passed to the open reference (OTU) picking and assigning workflow (described below). ITS sequences followed a similar protocol, except the ITS1 region was extracted from the illumine R1 read (Bengtsson-Palme et al. 2013) prior to OTU picking. In all cases, operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) were clustered at 97 % sequence similarity using UPARSE (Edgar et al. 2013) and OTU abundance tables constructed by mapping reads to these OTUs (usearch_global, 97%). OTU abundance tables were rarefied at 9051 (16S rRNA gene), 5000 (fungal ITS region) and 5000 (Eukaryotic 18S rRNA gene) sequences/sample to ensure even sampling depth. The Shannon diversity index was calculated on rarefied OTU tables using Primer v7 (Clarke & Gorley 2015) for ten main groups of soil microbes and fauna: bacteria (16S rRNA gene), fungi (fungal ITS region) and stramenopiles, amoebozoa, annelida, arthropoda, excavata, rhizaria, rotifera and nematoda (eukaryotic 18S rRNA gene). We selected this metric for our study because it provides a robust and informative estimation of taxonomic diversity for microbial communities (Haegeman et al. 2013).

Soil properties analysis.

Soils were extracted in deionized water for 1 h to achieve a soil:solution ratio of 1:5. Soil pH was then determined using a combination pH electrode. Texture was determined as explained in Bissett et al.

(2016). *Climate*. Mean annual temperature (MAT) and Aridity Index (AI; mean annual precipitation/potential evapotranspiration) were derived from the Worldclim database (<http://www.worldclim.org>) (Hijmans et al. 2005; Zomer et al. 2008). Climate gaps in the dataset were completed using local and regional databases. For clarity, we used aridity [maximum AI value in the dataset–AI] instead of the aridity index (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013). We used aridity instead of mean annual precipitation, because aridity includes both mean annual precipitation and potential evapotranspiration, and is therefore a more accurate metric of the water availability at each site. Spatial and climate data collection were performed in ESRI ArcMap (ESRI 2011; Redlands, CA: Environmental Systems Research Institute).

Aboveground plant productivity.

We used the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) as our proxy of plant productivity (Pettorelli et al. 2005; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016). These data were obtained from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) aboard NASA's Terra satellites (<http://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). This productivity index is largely used in the current literature (Pettorelli et al. 2005; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016) and provides a global measure of the "greenness" of vegetation across Earth's landscapes for a given composite period, and thus acts as a proxy of photosynthetic activity and large-scale vegetation distribution (Pettorelli et al. 2005; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016). We calculated the monthly average value for this variable between the periods of 2011-2014 (0.1 degrees resolution), when all soil sampling was conducted.

Assessing soil fertility.

The BASE project contains information on multiple surrogates of soil fertility including soil organic carbon (a common proxy of organic matter), macronutrients (i.e., ammonium, nitrate, phosphorus, potassium and magnesium) and micronutrients (i.e., copper, sodium, iron, manganese, zinc and aluminium). A detailed explanation on the rationale of the selected variables is available in the supplementary information of this manuscript (Methods S1). The details and protocols for soil analyses are given in (Bissett et al. 2016). In brief, soil organic carbon was determined using the Walkley-Black method (Walkley & Black 1934). Ammonium and nitrate were determined from 2M KCl extracts. Available phosphorus was measured using the Colwell method (Walkley & Black 1934). Exchangeable aluminium, magnesium, potassium and sodium were determined using a 1:5 soil: water extraction. This test was used in combination with the $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}_2/\text{BaCl}_2$ extractable exchangeable cations test, where the value for water soluble exchangeable cations is subtracted from the value for $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}_2/\text{BaCl}_2$ extractable

exchangeable cations (Rayment & Higginson 1992). Finally, diethylene-triamine-pentaacetic acid (DTPA) extractable trace elements (copper, iron, manganese and zinc) were determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy following extraction with (DTPA) for 2h (Rayment & Higginson 1992).

Soil fertility and diversity indices.

To obtain a quantitative index of soil fertility for each sample, we first normalized (log-transformed when needed) and standardized each of our twelve surrogates of fertility using the Z-score transformation ((actual value - mean) / standard deviation) as described in Maestre et al. (2012), Wagg et al. (2014) and Delgado-Baquerizo et al. (2016). Following this, the standardized surrogates of fertility were averaged to obtain a soil fertility index (Maestre et al. 2012). Using the same approach, we obtained a quantitative index of soil biodiversity including the diversity (Shannon) of bacteria, fungi, and multiple eukaryote communities (stramenopiles, amoebozoa, annelida, arthropoda, excavata, rhizaria, rotifera and nematoda) as described in Wagg et al. (2014) and Allan et al. (2014). This approach allowed us to evaluate links between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity in an integrative manner, rather than focusing on a particular component of the soil community or surrogate of fertility, which may not accurately represent the highly interactive nature of consumer-resource interactions during nutrient cycling (Wardle et al. 2004; Bardgett & van der Putten 2014; Wagg et al. 2014; Nielsen et al. 2015). As such, the effect from soil biodiversity on fertility and plant productivity will be a combined result of the close interaction among highly diverse groups of soil fauna and microbes. For example, groups of soil fauna, such as arthropods (*e.g.*, ants and termites) and annelids (*e.g.*, earthworms), play an essential role in helping to incorporate dead organic material into the soil (Nielsen et al. 2015), and bringing it into contact with microbial degraders. Additionally soil microbial communities degrade recalcitrant components of organic matter into more labile molecules (Schimel et al. 2005), releasing soil nutrients, and supporting essential ecosystem services.

Statistical analysis.

We first tested for differences in soil biodiversity and fertility between soil layers using one-way ANOVA with soil layer as a fixed factor; and conducted linear regression analyses in order to evaluate the relationship between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for the upper (0-10 cm) and lower (20-30 cm) layers. We repeated these analyses within characteristics biomes: tropical, temperate and arid ecosystems (Köppen classification), as well as croplands. In addition, we evaluated the relationship between the diversity of individual groups of organisms and soil fertility.

We then used structural equation modeling (SEM; Grace 2006) to obtain a system-level mechanistic understanding on the direct and indirect relationships between distance from the equator (absolute latitude), altitude, aridity, mean annual temperature, percentage of clay, soil-pH, plant productivity, soil biodiversity and fertility. This approach further allowed us to evaluate whether the links between soil biodiversity, fertility and above-ground plant productivity were maintained after accounting for multiple factors simultaneously. We conducted independent SEMs for each soil layer to provide insights on the tripartite linkages between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for the upper and lower layers; and to further evaluate the relative importance of key drivers of primary productivity, soil biodiversity and soil fertility (*i.e.*, geolocation, climate and soil properties) at different depths. The use of SEM is particularly useful in large scale correlative studies, as it allows us to partition causal influences among multiple variables, and to separate the direct and indirect effects of the predictors included in the model (Grace 2006). The first step in SEM requires establishing an *a priori* model based on known effects and relationships among the drivers of soil fertility (Fig. S1). Some data manipulation was required prior to modeling to improve the normality and linearity of our data. Altitude and percentage of clay were log-transformed to improve normality. Similarly, distance from equator and aridity were x^2 -transformed and MAT was square-root transformed. With a good model fit (see below), we were free to interpret the path coefficients of the model and their associated *P* values. A path coefficient is analogous to the partial correlation coefficient, and describes the strength and sign of the relationship between two variables (Grace 2006). Since some of the variables introduced were not normally distributed, the probability that a path coefficient differs from zero was tested using bootstrap resampling (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013). Bootstrapping is preferred to the classical maximum-likelihood estimation in these cases, because in bootstrapping probability assessments are not based on the assumption that data follows a particular theoretical distribution. Thus, data are randomly sampled with replacement in order to arrive at estimates of standard errors that are empirically associated with the distribution of the data found in the samples (Grace 2006). When these data manipulations were completed, we parameterized our model using our dataset and tested its overall goodness of fit. There is no single universally accepted test of overall goodness of fit for SEM, applicable in all situations regardless of sample size or data distribution. We used the Chi-square test (χ^2 ; the model has a good fit when $0 \leq \chi^2/\text{d.o.f} \leq 2$ and $0.05 < P \leq 1.00$) (Schermelleh-Engel et al. 2013) and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA; the model has a good fit when $0 \leq \text{RMSEA} \leq 0.05$ and $0.10 < P \leq 1.00$) (Schermelleh-Engel et al. 2013). Additionally, and because some variables were not normal, we confirmed the fit of the model using the Bollen-Stine bootstrap test (the model has a good fit when $0.10 < \text{bootstrap } P \leq 1.00$) (Schermelleh-Engel

et al. 2013). Our *a priori* model attained an acceptable fit by all criteria, and thus no post hoc alterations were made. All the SEM analyses were conducted using AMOS 20.0 (AMOS IBM, USA).

Results

Both soil biodiversity and fertility were significantly higher in the upper compared to the lower soil layer (Figs. 2a and 3), for bacteria, fungi and microbial eukaryotes, with a strong correlations observed between soil layers and biodiversity (Spearman's $\rho = 0.605$; $P < 0.001$) as well as fertility (Spearman's $\rho = 0.791$; $P < 0.001$). Most importantly, we showed that the stronger tripartite linkages among soil biodiversity, fertility and aboveground plant productivity were in the upper, compared to the lower, soil layer (Figs. 2b-d). Note that soil biodiversity (calculated as Shannon diversity indices) was positively and strongly related to the alpha diversity calculated from species richness (Fig. S2). In fact, similar results were obtained when using soil biodiversity calculated from species richness indices (Fig. S3), indicating that our results are robust to the choice of soil biodiversity metric. Moreover, the stronger correlations between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity at the upper layer were apparent when exploring the relationship between the diversity of single soil communities (Amoebozoa, Annelida, Arthropoda, Excavata, Rhizaria, Rotifera, Stramenopiles, Nematoda and Fungi) and both the fertility index and individual surrogates of fertility (Table S2; Fig. 4).

Structural equation models explained 79 % of the variation found in plant productivity. The proportion of explained variation in soil biodiversity (24 % in surface vs 9 % down under) and fertility (74 vs. 63%) was substantially greater in the upper than the lower layers (Fig. 5a, b) (our *a priori* model is available in Fig. S1). We found strong positive associations, including direct and indirect effects, among soil biodiversity, fertility and aboveground plant productivity in the upper layer (0-10cm; Fig. 5a), but not in the lower layer (20-30cm; Fig. 5b), after accounting for multiple environmental drivers, such as distance from equator, altitude, climate and soil properties. In particular, we found that the strong positive associations among soil biodiversity-fertility and fertility-aboveground plant productivity are limited to the upper layer of soil (0-10cm; Fig. 5). In addition, we found direct and significant negative effects of increasing aridity and mean annual temperature on soil biodiversity, fertility and aboveground plant productivity in the upper soil layer. However, only aridity continued to explain variation in soil biodiversity in the deeper soil layer. Finally, we found positive and significant direct effects of percentage of clay on soil fertility, which was stronger in the deeper soil layer (Fig. 5a, b).

The stronger relationship between soil biodiversity and fertility, as well as fertility and aboveground plant production in the upper layer compared to the lower layer of soil was, in general, maintained within major biomes including tropical, temperate and arid ecosystems (Fig. 6). The only

exception to this was croplands, where the relationship between soil biodiversity and fertility was disrupted for both soil layers and the relationship between fertility and plant productivity became negative for the lower layer of soil (Fig. 6). However, in general, we found strong reductions in soil biodiversity and fertility with depth for all ecosystem types including croplands (Fig. 6).

Discussion

This study provides, to our knowledge, the first empirical evidence showing that on a continental scale the positive effects of soil biodiversity-fertility and fertility-aboveground productivity are limited to topsoil (above 20cm depth). In these topsoils we also show that tripartite, positive feedback relationships between diversity of microbial and invertebrate-based soil food webs, fertility and plant productivity, are universal across soil types and climates, and that they are comparatively weaker in lower soil layers, even at the shallow depths we studied. Furthermore, our results provide an integrated view of how climate and soil factors influence soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity at the continental scale and across two different soil depths, which is critical to improving soil carbon and Earth system simulation models as well as for formulating sustainable ecosystem management and conservation policies.

Most importantly, we used SEM to build a system-level understanding of the drivers of soil biodiversity, fertility and plant production in terrestrial ecosystems in the two different soil layers. This ultimately allowed us to evaluate if the reported positive associations among soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity are maintained across soil layers after accounting for important environmental factors such as spatial parameters, climates, soils texture and pH. In agreement with recent studies, our model provides strong evidence for a negative impact of increasing aridity and mean annual temperature on soil biodiversity at multiple trophic levels, on soil fertility and on plant productivity (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013; 2016; Maestre et al. 2015) in surface soils. This effect is lost in deeper soils, where only aridity continues to explain variation in soil biodiversity. Supporting the robustness of our results, we found a strong positive link between percentage of clay and soil fertility, which was stronger in the deeper soil layer. Clay is well-known to be one of the main drivers of soil fertility in terrestrial ecosystems (Brady & Weil 2002). We identified strong positive associations (including direct and indirect effects) among soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity in the upper layer (0-10cm), but not in the lower layer (20-30cm). In particular, we found a decoupling of soil fertility-plant productivity and soil biodiversity-fertility relationships for the lower layer. These results provide strong support for the hypothesis that the positive linkages among soil diversity, fertility and plant productivity are largely limited to a thin surface soil layer of a few centimeters.

The co-occurrence of resource inputs from aboveground communities (e.g., amount and diversity of litter; Hooper 2000), and of high levels of soil diversity from multiple trophic levels in the top 10cm of soil may explain the highest link between soil biodiversity and fertility for this layer. The lack of relationship between soil fertility and plant productivity below the topsoil may be related to the lower fertility found between 20-30cm and the reports of greatest plant nutrient uptake in the top 10cm of soil (Jackson 1988). Interestingly, the bivariate direct positive relationship between soil biodiversity and aboveground plant productivity was maintained for both soil layers. Although the indirect positive effects between soil biodiversity and plant productivity via soil fertility were limited to the upper soil layer (Fig. 2), other mutual benefits for aboveground plant production (from soil biodiversity) and soil biodiversity (from aboveground plant production) may still occur in the lower layer of soil. For instance, higher plant production may still benefit the diversity of root/microbe consumers and decomposers, e.g., nematodes and fungi, at 20-30cm depth (Nielsen et al. 2015; Table S2). Also, higher plant productivity may promote water acquisition and storage from which soil fauna could strongly benefit. Similarly, a relatively high soil biodiversity within the lower soil layer may promote plant productivity by providing defense to plants against pests and the invasion of soil borne pathogens (van Elsas et al. 2012).

In general, the positive correlations between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for the upper layer were maintained across major biomes, i.e., “natural” ecosystems from arid, temperate and tropical regions. They also remain valid when exploring the relationship between soil diversity at multiple trophic levels (Amoebozoa, Annelida, Arthropoda, Excavata, Rhizaria, Rotifera, Stramenopiles, Nematoda and Fungi; Fig. 4 and Table S2), and regardless of whether the fertility index or individual surrogates of fertility are used (Table S2). An interesting exception was the diversity of bacteria, which showed a negative relationship with soil fertility and plant productivity (Table S2). However, we still found a positive effect of bacteria on nitrate availability, highlighting the robustness of our data, as nitrification is largely controlled by prokaryotes (Robertson & Groffman 2007; Table S2). This result is supported by a recent global study that reported a higher positive influence of fungal diversity (*vs.* bacterial diversity) on multiple ecosystem functions related to nutrient cycling in nutrient-poor dryland ecosystem soils (Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016), a common condition observed for Australian soils (Orians & Milewski 2007).

Our results have important implications for soil ecosystem functioning under global change scenarios. They suggest that any loss of surface soil could break the link between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity, all essential components of ecosystem functioning. Indeed, it is predicted that ongoing processes such as climate change, land use intensification and desertification will lead to significant surface soil loss in the near to medium term (Banwart 2011). For example, agricultural

intensification and increases in aridity linked to climate change (Huang et al. 2016) can potentially reduce permanent plant cover and promote physical processes such as wind-blown sand and abrasion of exposed rock surfaces, increasing the already high rates at which soils are eroded. In ecosystems where soils (e.g. croplands) are subject to strong anthropogenic pressures or are vulnerable to erosion, the strong linkage between biodiversity and soil fertility could be weakened. In support of this argument, we found no relationship between soil biodiversity and fertility in cropland samples (Fig. 6k). Thus, our results suggest that erosion of soils may weaken the strong linkage between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity. Note that, even if erosion impacts only the linkage between soil biodiversity-fertility and/or fertility-plant production and/or plant production-soil biodiversity, these impacts may still have cascading effects on entire food web with consequences for plant productivity and other ecosystem functions. Given that the highest soil biodiversity is found in the upper soil layer (Fig. 2), after losing the upper layer of soil through erosion, it may take centuries or millennia for the new topsoil to start acting as the former one given microbial dispersal/colonization dynamics (especially for fungi and soil fauna; Powell et al. 2015) and evolutionary rates.

Our results further reinforce the recently proposed concept of the soil critical zone, which is currently measured in meters, but our work suggests it may be limited to the more vulnerable top few centimeters of soil only (Pointing & Belnap 2012). Furthermore, our results suggest that the relationship between soil biodiversity and fertility, and its positive effects for plant production, are an intrinsic property of this thin, but critical and vulnerable, layer of Earth's skin. Interestingly, the influence of environmental factors (including spatial distance, climate and soil properties) on our response variables was also significantly greater for the upper layer. Thus, the ability of climate (i.e., mean annual temperature) and spatial factors (i.e., distance from equator) to predict soil biodiversity and fertility is reduced under conditions of weakened diversity-fertility relationships. This has consequences for understanding how global change, particularly aridity, will impact soil fertility in the coming decades. Interestingly, the negative effects of aridity on soil biodiversity were maintained across both soil layers.

Altogether, our findings indicate that the often positive theoretical linkages of soil biodiversity at multiple trophic levels, fertility and plant production are ubiquitous in terrestrial ecosystems at large scales, but limited only to a thin layer of the soil close to surface. Below the surface layer, the relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity weaken considerably. These findings provide a novel framework to predict impacts of soil loss and degradation. By revealing the relationships between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity, which underpin critical ecosystem functions and services on which humans depend, we can begin to formulate appropriate soil

and plant productivity management and conservation policies respond to likely changes in ecosystem functioning under future environments.

Acknowledgments

We would like to acknowledge the contribution of the BASE project partners DOI 10.4227/71/561c9bc670099, an initiative supported by Bioplatforms Australia with funds provided by the Australian Commonwealth Government through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy. We thank the Biomes of Australian Soil Environments (BASE) project and its contributors (<https://downloads.bioplatforms.com/base/acknowledgements>) for sequence and edaphic data used in this work. The data used in this study is available from the BASE data portal (<https://downloads.bioplatforms.com/base/>). M.D-B. and B.K.S. acknowledge support from the Australian Research Council (project DP13010484; DP170104634). M.D-B. also acknowledge support from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme H2020-MSCA-IF-2016 under REA grant agreement n° 702057.

Author contributions

M.D-B. designed this study and analyzed data from the BASE project in consultation with A.B., J.R.P. and B.K.S. All the authors except M.D-B., B.K.S., J.R.P. conducted field surveys and collected the soils used in this study under the coordination of A.B. M.D-B. conducted statistical modeling. A.B. conducted bioinformatics analyses. The manuscript was written by M.D-B with contributions from all co-authors.

Data accessibility

The primary data used in this study is available in Table S1. The raw sequence data has been deposited in the Sequence Read Archive from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (USA)(<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>). The SRA accession number for each sample is available in Table S1.

References

Allan, E., Bossdorf, O., Dormann, C.F., Prati, D., Gossner, M.M., Tschardtke, T., Blüthgen, N., Bellach, M., Birkhofer, K., Boch, S., Böhm, S., Börschig, C., Chatzinotas, A., Christ, S., Daniel, R., Diekötter, T., Fischer, C., Friedl, T., Glaser, K. et al. (2014). Interannual variation in land-use intensity enhances grassland multidiversity. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 111, 308-13.

- Andrews S. (2010). FastQC A Quality Control tool for High Throughput Sequence Data. Available online at: <http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc>.
- Banwart, S. (2011). Save our soils. *Nature* 474, 151–152.
- Bardgett R.D., van der Putten, W.H. (2014). Belowground biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. *Nature* 515, 505–511.
- Bengtsson-Palme J, Ryberg M, Hartmann M, Branco S, Wang Z, Godhe A, et al. (2013). Improved software detection and extraction of ITS1 and ITS2 from ribosomal ITS sequences of fungi and other eukaryotes for analysis of environmental sequencing data. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 4, 914–919.
- Bissett, A., Fitzgerald, A., Meintjes, T., Mele, P.M., Reith, R., Dennis, P.G., Breed, M.F., Brown, B., Brown, M.K., Brugger, J., Byrne, M., Caddy-Retalic, S., Carmody, B., Coates, D.J., et al. (2016). Introducing BASE: the Biomes of Australian Soil Environments soil microbial diversity database. *GigaScience* 20165, 21.
- Brady, N.C., Weil. R.R. (2002). *The Nature and Properties of Soils* (13th ed. Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA).
- Clarke, K.R., Gorley, R.N. (2015). *PRIMER v7: User Manual/Tutorial*. PRIMER-E, Plymouth, 296pp.
- Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Maestre, F.T., Gallardo, A., Bowker, M.A., Wallenstein, M.D., Quero, J.L., Ochoa, V., Gozalo, B., García-Gómez, M., Soliveres, S., García-Palacios, P., Berdugo, M., Valencia, E., Escolar, C., Arredondo, T., Barraza-Zepeda, C., Bran, D., Carreira, J.A., Chaieb, M., Conceição, A.A., Derak, M., Eldridge, D.J. et al. (2013). Decoupling of soil nutrient cycles as a function of aridity in global drylands. *Nature* 502, 672-6.
- Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Maestre, F.T., Reich, P.B., Jeffries, T.C., Gaitan, J.J., Encinar, D., Berdugo, M., Campbell, C.D., Singh, B.K (2016). Microbial diversity drives multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems. *Nat Commun.* 7:10541.
- Edgar, R.C. (2013). UPARSE: highly accurate OTU sequences from microbial amplicon reads. *Nature Methods* 10, 996–998.
- Gans, J., Wolinsky, M., Dunbar, J. (2005). Computational improvements reveal great bacterial diversity and high metal toxicity in soil. *Science* 26, 1387-90.
- Grace, J.B. (2006) *Structural Equation Modeling Natural Systems* (Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, UK).
- Haegeman, B., Hamelin, J., Moriarty J., Neal, P., Dushoff, J., Weitz, J.S. (2013). Robust estimation of microbial diversity in theory and in practice. *ISME J.* 7, 1092–1101.
- Hijmans, R.J., S.E. Cameron, J.L. Parra, P.G. Jarvis, J.A. (2005). Very high resolution interpolated climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology* 25, 1965-1978.

- Hol, W.H., de Boer, W., de Hollander, M., Kuramae, E.E., Meisner, A., van der Putten, W.H (2015). Context dependency and saturating effects of loss of rare soil microbes on plant productivity. *Front. Plant. Sci.* 6, 485.
- Hooper, D.U., D.E. Bignell, V.K. Brown, L. Brussaard, J.M. Dangerfield, D.H. Wall, D.A. Wardle, D.C. Coleman, K.E. Giller, P. Lavelle, W.H. v. d. Putten, P.C. d. Rüter, J. Rusek, W.L. Silver, J.M. Tiedje, Wolters, V. (2000). Interactions between aboveground and belowground biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems: patterns, mechanisms, and feedbacks. *BioScience* 50, 1049-1061.
- Huang, J., Yu, H., Guan, X., Wang, G., Guo, R. (2016). Accelerated dryland expansion under climate change. *Nat Clim Change* 6, 166–171
- Jobbágy, E.G., Jackson, R.B. (2000). The vertical distribution of soil organic carbon and its relation to climate and vegetation. *Ecol. Appl.* 10, 423–436.
- Jobbágy, E.G., Jackson, R.B. (2001). The distribution of soil nutrients with depth: Global patterns and the imprint of plants. *Biogeochemistry* 53, 51-77.
- Jackson, L. E. Strauss, R. B., Firestone, M. K., Bartolome, J. W. (1988). Plant and soil nitrogen dynamics in California annual grassland. *Plant Soil* 110, 9–17
- Lane, D.J. (1991). *Nucleic Acid Techniques in Bacterial Systematics* (John Wiley and Sons, NY, USA).
- Maestre, F.T., Quero, J.L., Gotelli, N.J., Escudero, A., Ochoa, V., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., García-Gómez, M., Bowker, M.A., Soliveres, S., Escolar, C., García-Palacios, P., Berdugo, M., Valencia, E., Gozalo, B., Gallardo, A., Aguilera, L., Arredondo, T. et al. (2012). Plant species richness and ecosystem multifunctionality in global drylands. *Science* 335, 214-8.
- Maestre, F.T., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Jeffries, T.C., Eldridge, D.J., Ochoa, V., Gozalo, B., Quero, J.L., García-Gómez, M., Gallardo, A., Ulrich, W., Bowker, M.A., Arredondo, T. et al. (2015). Increasing aridity reduces soil microbial diversity and abundance in global drylands. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 112, 15684-9.
- Magoč, T., Salzberg, S.L. (2011). FLASH: fast length adjustment of short reads to improve genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics* 27, 2957-63.
- Nielsen, U.N., Wall, D.H., Six, J. (2015). Soil Biodiversity and the Environment. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 40, 63-90.
- Orians, G.H., Milewski, A.V. (2007). Ecology of Australia: the effects of nutrient-poor soils and intense fires. *Biol Rev Camb Philos Soc.* 82, 393-423.
- Pettorelli, N., Vik, J.O., Myrsetrud, A., Gaillard, J.M., Tucker, C.J., Stenseth, N.C. (2005). Using the satellite-derived NDVI to assess ecological responses to environmental change. *Trends Ecol Evol.* 20, 503-10.

- Pointing, S.B., Belnap, J. (2012). Microbial colonization and controls in dryland systems. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 10, 551-62.
- Powell, J.R., Karunaratne, S.B., Campbell, C.D., Yao, H., Robinson, L., & Singh, B.K. (2015). Deterministic processes vary during community assembly for ecologically dissimilar taxa. *Nat Commun.* 6: 8444.
- Rayment, G.E., Higginson, F.R. (1992). Australian Laboratory Handbook of Soil and Water Chemical Methods (Reed International Books Australia P/L, trading as Inkata Press, Port Melbourne, Australia).
- Reith, F., Zammit, C.M., Pohrib, R., Gregg, A.L. Wakelin, S.A. (2015). Geogenic Factors as Drivers of Microbial Community Diversity in Soils Overlying Polymetallic Deposits. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 81, 7822-7832.
- Robertson, G.P., Groffman, P. (2007). Soil microbiology and biochemistry (Ecology Springer, New York).
- Schermelleh-Engel, K., Moosbrugger, H., Muller, H. (2003). Evaluating the Fit of Structural Equation Models: Tests of Significance and Descriptive Goodness-of-Fit Measures. *Methods of Psychological Research Online* 8, 23.
- Schimel, J.P., Bennett, J., Fierer, N. (2005). Biological diversity and function in soils (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK).
- Schloss, P.D., Westcott, S.L., Ryabin, T., Hall, J.R., Hartmann, M., Hollister, E.B., Lesniewski, R.A., Oakley, B.B., Parks, D.H., Robinson, C.J., et al. (2009). Introducing mothur: Open-Source, Platform-Independent, Community-Supported Software for Describing and Comparing Microbial Communities. *Appl. Environ. Microb.* 75, 7537-7541.
- Soliveres, S., van der Plas, F., Manning, P., Prati, P., Gossner, Renner, S.C., M.M, Alt, F., Arndt, H., Baumgartner, V., Binkenstein, J., Birkhofer, K., Blaser, S., Blüthgen, N., Boch, S., Böhm, S., Börschig, C., Buscot, F., Diekötter, T., Heinze, J., Hölzel, N., Jung, K., Klaus, V.H., Klein, A., Kleinebecker, T., Klemmer, S., Krauss, J., Lange, M., Morris, E.K., Müller, J., Oelmann, Y., Overmann J., Pašalić, E., Renne, S.C., Rillig, M.C., Schaefer, H.M., Schloter. M., Schmitt, B., Schöning, I., Schrupf, M., Sikorski, J., Socher, S.A., Solly, E.F., Sonnemann, I., Sorkau, E., Steckel, J., Steffen-Dewenter, I., Stempfhuber, B., Tschapka, M., Türke, M., Venter, P., Weiner, C.N., Weisser, W.W., Werner, M., Westphal, C., Wilcke, W., Wolters, V., Wubet, T., Wurst, S., Fischer, M., Allan, E. (2016). Biodiversity at multiple trophic levels is needed for ecosystem multifunctionality. *Nature* 536, 456-459

- van der Heijden, M.G., Bardgett, R.D., van Straalen, N.M. (2008). The unseen majority: soil microbes as drivers of plant diversity and productivity in terrestrial ecosystems. *Ecol Lett.* 11, 296-310.
- van Elsas, J.D., Chiurazzi, M., Mallon, C.A., Elhottova, D., Kristufek, V., Salles, J.F. (2012). Microbial diversity determines the invasion of soil by a bacterial pathogen. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 109, 1159-64.
- Wall, D.H., Bardgett, R.D., Kelly, E. (2010). Biodiversity in the dark. *Nature Geoscience* 3, 297-298.
- Wall D.H., Nielsen, U.N., Six, J. (2015). Soil biodiversity and human health. *Nature* 528, 69–76.
- Wagg, C., Bender, S.F., Widmer, F., van der Heijden, M.G. (2014). Soil biodiversity and soil community composition determine ecosystem multifunctionality. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 8, 5266-70.
- Walkley, A., Black. I.A. (1934). An Examination of Degtjareff Method for Determining Soil Organic Matter and a Proposed Modification of the Chromic Acid Titration Method. *Soil Sci.* 37, 29-37.
- Wardle, D.A., Bardgett, R.D., Klironomos, J.N., Setälä, H., van der Putten, W.H., Wall, D.H. (2004). Ecological Linkages Between Aboveground and Belowground Biota. *Science* 304, 1629.
- White, T.J., Bruns, T., Lee, S. and Taylor, J., (1990). Amplification and direct sequencing of fungal ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetics. Chapter 38. Pages 315-322. In: Innis MA, Gelfand DH, Sninsky JJ, White TJ eds. *PCR Protocols: a Guide to Methods and Applications* (Academic Press, Orlando, Florida, USA).
- World Bank (2008). *World Development Report, Agriculture for Development* (World Bank, Washington, DC, USA).
- Zomer, R., Trabucco, A., van Straaten, O., Bossio, D. (2006). Carbon, land and water: a global analysis of the hydrologic dimensions of climate change mitigation through afforestation / reforestation. Colombo, Sri Lanka: International Water Management Institute (IWMI) 38p. (IWMI Research Report 101).

Figure 1. Location of study sites (n = 289).

Figure 2. Relationship between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity across different soil depths. Panel (a) represents the Z-score values (mean \pm SE) for soil biodiversity and fertility in the upper layer (0-10cm) and lower layer (20-30cm). Significance levels of each predictor are as follows: *** $P < 0.001$. Panels (b), (c) and (d) represent the linear regression between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for two different soil layers. Solid and dashed lines represent linear regressions fitted to the upper and lower layers, respectively.

Figure 3. Mean (\pm SE) values for the diversity of soil microbes and fauna in the upper layer (0-10cm) and lower layer (20-30cm). Significance levels of each predictor are as follows: *** $P < 0.001$. “nats” are the units for Shannon diversity calculated using the natural logarithm.

Figure 4. Relationship between the diversity of particular groups of soil microbes and fauna (panels a to j) with fertility in the upper layer (0-10cm) and lower layer (20-30cm). Solid and dashed lines represent linear regressions fitted to the upper and lower layers, respectively. “nats” are the units for Shannon diversity calculated using the natural logarithm.

Figure 5. Direct and indirect effects of space, climate and soil properties on soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity derived from SEM in the upper (a) and lower soil layers (b). Numbers adjacent to arrows are indicative of the effect size (bootstrap P -value) of the relationship. The width of arrows is proportional to the strength of path coefficients. R^2 denotes the proportion of variance explained. MAT = Mean annual temperature.

Figure 6. Relationship between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity across different soil depths for arid ($n = 66$), temperate ($n = 159$), tropical ($n = 17$) and agricultural ($n = 47$) regions. Panels (a, d, g and j) represent the Z-score values (mean \pm SE) for soil biodiversity and fertility in the upper layer (0-10cm) and lower layer (20-30cm). Significance levels of each predictor are as follows: $^{\circ}P < 0.100$, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$ and $***P < 0.001$. Panels (d, c, e, f, h, i, k and l) represent the linear regression between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for two different soil layers. Solid and dashed lines represent linear regressions fitted to the upper and lower layers, respectively.

Supporting information

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Methods S1. Rationale on the included surrogates of soil fertility in this study.

Table S1. Primary data used in this study including information on location, soil layer, biome types, climate, soil properties, soil biodiversity, fertility and above-ground plant productivity.

Table S2. Correlations between soil diversity and fertility. Spearman correlations between plant productivity, the diversity of single soil microbial and animal communities and multiple surrogates of soil fertility.

Figure S1. A priori structural equation model including direct and indirect effects of space, climate and soil properties on soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity.

Figure S2. Relationship between soil biodiversity calculated from Shannon diversity and species richness (number of OTUs) and across different soil depths.

Figure S3. Relationship between soil biodiversity (calculated from species richness – number of OTUs), fertility and plant productivity across different soil depths.

***New Phytologist* Supporting Information**

Article title: Circular linkages between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity are limited to topsoil at the continental scale

Authors: Manuel Delgado-Baquerizo, Jeff R. Powell, Kelly Hamonts, Frank Reith, Pauline Mele, Mark V. Brown, Paul G. Dennis, Belinda C. Ferrari, Anna Fitzgerald, Andrew Young, Brajesh K. Singh & Andrew Bissett

Article acceptance date: 27 April 2017

The following Supporting Information is available for this article:

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Methods S1. Rationale on the included surrogates of soil fertility in this study.

The BASE project contains information on multiple surrogates of soil fertility including soil organic carbon (a common proxy of organic matter), macronutrients (i.e., ammonium, nitrate, phosphorus, potassium and magnesium) and micronutrients (i.e., copper, aluminium, sodium, iron, manganese and zinc). Overall, these variables constitute a good proxy of nutrient cycling, biological productivity, and buildup of nutrient pools (Reiss et al. 2009; Jax 2010; Maestre et al. 2012). In particular, organic C is a good proxy of decomposition and organic matter content in soil, with important implications for climate regulation (Jax 2010). Nitrogen and phosphorus are the nutrients that most frequently limit primary production in terrestrial ecosystems (Schlesinger et al. 1996; Vitousek et al. 2002). For example,

ammonium and nitrate are important N sources for both microorganisms and plants (Schlesinger et al. 1996). Inorganic P is the main P source for plants and microorganisms, and its availability is linked to the desorption and dissolution of P from soil minerals, and to a lesser extent, to the decomposition of organic matter (Schlesinger et al. 1996; Vitousek et al. 2002; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2013). Potassium (K) is the most abundant cation in plant cells and is the second most abundant nutrient after N in leaves (Sardans & Peñuelas 2015). This nutrient is involved in key processes, such as the formation of carbohydrates and proteins, and the regulation of internal plant moisture and photosynthesis. Magnesium is a key constituent of the chlorophyll molecule playing a key role in photosynthesis. Finally, copper, aluminum, sodium, iron, manganese and zinc are important elements involved in either microbial, animal or plant metabolisms (Schlesinger et al. 1996).

Table S1. Primary data used in this study including information on location, soil layer, biome types, climate, soil properties, soil biodiversity, fertility and above-ground plant productivity.

Table S1 is available online as a Separate Excel file under the Supporting Information for this article.

1 **Table S2. Correlations between soil diversity and fertility.** Spearman correlations between plant productivity, the diversity of single soil
 2 microbial and animal communities and multiple surrogates of soil fertility. Upper layer = top 0-10cm; Lower layer = 20-30cm. Significance
 3 levels of each predictor are as follows: ^a*P* < 0.10, **P* < 0.05 and ***P* < 0.01.

Element	Zone	Plant productivity	Soil biodiversity	Stramenopiles	Amoebozoa	Annelida	Arthropoda	Excavata	Rhizaria	Rotifera	Nematoda	Fungi	Bacteria
Plant productivity	Upper layer		0.502**	0.358**	-0.018	0.540**	0.628**	0.155**	0.393**	0.440**	0.649**	0.278*	-
	Lower layer		0.319**	0.312**	0.014	0.374**	0.315**	-0.049	0.427**	0.429**	0.415**	0.077	0.400**
Soil fertility	Upper layer	0.449**	0.433**	0.416**	0.169**	0.486**	0.390**	0.207**	0.315**	0.265**	0.386**	0.324*	-0.119*
	Lower layer	0.267**	0.217**	0.260**	0.285**	0.237**	0.186**	-0.048	0.210**	0.132*	0.075	0.082	-0.132*
Soil organic carbon	Upper layer	0.667**	0.533**	0.460**	0.118*	0.553**	0.561**	0.215**	0.443**	0.392**	0.595**	0.360*	-0.138*
	Lower layer	0.579**	0.303**	0.278**	0.235**	0.260**	0.311**	0.027	0.328**	0.305**	0.280**	0.135*	0.322**
Ammonium	Upper layer	0.589**	0.416**	0.335**	-0.017	0.491**	0.483**	0.121*	0.358**	0.374**	0.527**	0.238*	-
	Lower layer	0.535**	0.195**	0.196**	0.120*	0.267**	0.215**	-0.023	0.232**	0.293**	0.255**	0.009	0.352**
Nitrate	Upper layer	-0.131*	0.112 ^a	0.233**	0.356**	0.03	-0.103 ^a	0.173**	0.142*	-0.048	-0.072	0.110 ^a	0.173**
	Lower layer	-0.178**	0.124*	0.161**	0.361**	0.021	-0.038	0.049	0.048	-0.088	0.006	0.04	0.282**
Phosphorus	Upper layer	0.227**	0.357**	0.405**	0.279**	0.318**	0.196**	0.232**	0.257**	0.153**	0.223**	0.248*	0.035
	Lower layer	0.295**	0.350**	0.382**	0.281**	0.278**	0.143*	0.055	0.345**	0.206**	0.156**	0.192*	0.067
Copper	Upper layer	0.079	0.260**	0.263**	0.223**	0.195**	0.149*	0.163**	0.144*	0.095	0.076	0.264*	0.102 ^a
	Lower layer	-0.072	0.091	0.098 ^a	0.202**	0.093	0.039	-0.134*	0.016	-0.002	-0.066	0.067	0.159**

Aluminum	Upper layer	0.589**	0.008	-0.074	-0.336**	0.201**	0.278**	-0.170**	-0.016	0.138*	0.201**	-0.05	-
	Lower layer	0.535**	-0.054	-0.095	-0.259**	0.116*	0.034	-0.176**	0.082	0.247**	0.128*	-0.057	0.462**
Magnesium	Upper layer	-0.043	0.293**	0.283**	0.305**	0.199**	0.117*	0.269**	0.178**	0.110 ^a	0.075	0.278*	0.154**
	Lower layer	-0.302**	0.108 ^a	0.173**	0.328**	-0.006	0.004	0.026	0.001	-0.087	-0.125*	0.059	0.204**
Potassium	Upper layer	-0.098 ^a	0.104 ^a	0.151*	0.155**	0.083	-0.004	0.094	0.05	-0.039	-0.088	0.195*	0.008
	Lower layer	-0.310**	-0.089	-0.038	0.034	-0.142*	-0.064	-0.036	-0.065	0.188**	-0.234**	-0.01	0.151**
Sodium	Upper layer	-0.093	0.057	0.100 ^a	0.230**	0.038	0.019	0.082	0.033	-0.04	-0.058	0.056	-0.081
	Lower layer	-0.250**	-0.005	0.084	0.300**	-0.028	-0.019	0.005	-0.079	0.192**	-0.123*	-0.031	0.056
Iron	Upper layer	0.658**	0.517**	0.427**	0.094	0.555**	0.584**	0.163**	0.407**	0.424**	0.614**	0.352*	0.158**
	Lower layer	0.600**	0.351**	0.353**	0.179**	0.417**	0.294**	-0.057	0.417**	0.308**	0.343**	0.106 ^a	0.296**
Manganese	Upper layer	0.228**	0.304**	0.286**	0.036	0.269**	0.240**	0.111 ^a	0.236**	0.212**	0.229**	0.309*	-0.019
	Lower layer	0.143*	0.140*	0.171**	0.151**	0.109 ^a	0.083	-0.032	0.157**	0.025	0.012	0.069	0.064
Zinc	Upper layer	0.514**	0.492**	0.468**	0.111	0.527**	0.466**	0.181**	0.443**	0.347**	0.499**	0.374*	-0.068
	Lower layer	0.413**	0.271**	0.334**	0.193**	0.342**	0.265**	-0.024	0.293**	0.234**	0.157**	0.08	0.224**

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6 **Figure S1.** A priori structural equation model including direct and indirect effects of space, climate and
 7 soil properties on soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity. MAT = Mean annual temperature.

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10 **Figure S2. Relationship between soil biodiversity calculated from Shannon diversity and species**
11 **richness (number of OTUs) and across different soil depths. Solid and dashed lines represent linear**
12 **regressions fitted to upper (0-10cm) and lower (20-30cm) layers, respectively.**

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17 **Figure S3. Relationship between soil biodiversity (calculated from species richness – number of**
 18 **OTUs), fertility and plant productivity across different soil depths. Panel (a) represents the Z-score**
 19 **values for soil biodiversity in the upper layer (0-10cm) and lower layer (20-30cm). Significance levels**
 20 **of each predictor are as follows: *** $P < 0.001$. Panels (b), (c), (d) and (e) represent the linear regression**
 21 **between soil biodiversity, fertility and plant productivity for two different soil layers. Solid and dashed**
 22 **lines represent linear regressions fitted to the upper and lower layers, respectively.**

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26 **References:**

- 27 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Maestre, F.T., Gallardo, A., Bowker, M.A., Wallenstein, M.D., Quero, J.L.,
28 Ochoa, V., Gozalo, B., García-Gómez, M., Soliveres, S., García-Palacios, P., Berdugo, M.,
29 Valencia, E., Escolar, C., Arredondo, T., Barraza-Zepeda, C., Bran, D., Carreira, J.A., Chaieb, M.,
30 Conceição, A.A., Derak, M., Eldridge, D.J. et al. (2013). Decoupling of soil nutrient cycles as a
31 function of aridity in global drylands. *Nature* 502, 672-6.
- 32 Jax, K. (2010). *Ecosystem Functioning* (Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, UK).
- 33 Maestre, F.T., Quero, J.L., Gotelli, N.J., Escudero, A., Ochoa, V., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., García-
34 Gómez, M., Bowker, M.A., Soliveres, S., Escolar, C., García-Palacios, P., Berdugo, M., Valencia,
35 E., Gozalo, B., Gallardo, A., Aguilera, L., Arredondo, T. et al. (2012). Plant species richness and
36 ecosystem multifunctionality in global drylands. *Science* 335, 214-8.
- 37 Reiss, J. R. Bridle, J. M. Montoya, G. Woodward (2009). Emerging horizons in biodiversity and
38 ecosystem functioning research. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 24, 505–514.
- 39 *Sardans, J., Peñuelas, J. (2015) Potassium: a neglected nutrient in global change. Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.*
40 *24, 261–275.*
- 41 Schlesinger, W.H. (1996). *Biogeochemistry, an analysis of global change* (Academic Press, San Diego,
42 CA, USA).
- 43 Vitousek, P.M., Cassman, K., Cleveland, C., Crews, T., Field, C.B., Grimm, N. B., Howarth, R.W., Marino,
44 R., Martinelli, L., Rastetter, E. B., Sprent, J. I. (2002). Towards an ecological understanding of
45 biological nitrogen fixation. *Biogeochemistry* 57, 1.

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